

Validation of non-invasive Mean Flow Index in Acute Ischemic Stroke Patients

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Abstract—The changes in cerebral blood flow velocity (CBFv) in response to the modulation of arterial blood pressure (ABP) allow the determination of aspects of cerebral autoregulation (CA). Different methods have been proposed in the literature to assess CA. Researchers from the Biomedical Engineering department at the Federal University of ABC (UFABC) and the Neurosonology and Cerebral Hemodynamics group at the Department of Neurology, School of Medicine, University of São Paulo (FMUSP) have developed an open-source clinical platform for CA evaluation, called the Cerebral Autoregulation Assessment Open Source (CAAos) platform. The methods of Transfer Function Analysis (TFA) and Autoregulation Index (ARI) are implemented along with a set of noise and artifact removal tools and visualization features. In this context, the present study aims to clinically validate the non-invasive mean flow index (nMxa) method in the CAAos platform. The validation is conducted by analyzing the difference in nMxa results between 22 Control Subjects and 23 Acute Ischemic Stroke Patients. This difference is evaluated through a one-way ANOVA test between the groups with two different separations. The validation of this method in the CAAos platform could contribute to multicenter studies in the evaluation of neurological diseases by leveraging its open-source code. This would facilitate a proper assessment of the AC mechanism, leading to a better understanding of the pathophysiology of neurological diseases, and aiding in the identification of patients at high risk of cerebral hemodynamic disorders.

Keywords — *Cerebral Autoregulation, nMxa Index, Ischemic Stroke, CAAos Platform, Validation by Statistical Analysis.*

I. Introduction

The human brain, a highly complex organ, requires a continuous and adequate supply of oxygen and nutrients to function properly [1]. This supply, obtained directly from the cerebral blood flow, is essential for the viability and functionality of neural components [1].

The necessary regulation in the process of circulating these supplies in the brain is achieved through the physiological mechanism known as Cerebral Autoregulation (CA). This mechanism is responsible for maintaining the

cerebral blood flow approximately constant, regardless of variations in blood pressure [2].

In this context, researchers from the University of Leicester have created a platform for investigating and analyzing CA, which is currently used as the gold standard by the Cerebral Autoregulation Network (CARNet - <http://www.car-net.org>) in brain hemodynamics research. However, even though it rigorously complies with CARNet requirements, the platform used in these studies was developed in the 1990s and is compatible only with the DOS operating system, making it incompatible with current systems and restricted to researchers from the University of Leicester. As a result, customizing parameters for new studies and incorporating new processing techniques are limited.

To overcome these limitations and advance in cerebral circulation assessment, researchers from the Federal University of ABC, in collaboration with the São Paulo University Medical School FMUSP group, have developed the Cerebral Autoregulation Assessment Open Source (CAAos) platform [3]. This innovative platform is implemented in Python 3, a current and high-level programming language compatible with the latest operating systems. It represents the world's first open-source clinical platform for cerebral circulation assessment and includes implemented and validated Transfer Function Analysis (TFA) and Autoregulation Index (ARI) methods, as well as tools for noise removal, data processing, and visualization. CAAos represents a significant advancement in cerebral circulation assessment and has the potential to provide a personalized and accurate approach in future studies. Its availability and technical documentation make it easy to use in clinical centers, contributing to the understanding of the mechanisms involved in cerebral regulation and enabling the development of more effective therapeutic approaches for neurological patients. This platform can be an important tool for the early detection of cerebral impairments in neurological conditions such as hemorrhagic or ischemic strokes.

Within the context of CA, one of the indices used to evaluate individuals' CA is the method known as Mean Flow Index (Mx). Introduced in the mid-1990s [4], the Mx index is a correlation coefficient between fluctuations in the cerebral blood flow velocity (CBFv) in the middle cerebral artery and the global cerebral perfusion pressure. Mx has been applied in various experimental and clinical scenarios [4]. In the CAAos

platform, a similar index known as nMxa is used instead of Mx. However, the nMxa method is calculated from the dynamic relationship between CBFv and mean arterial blood pressure (ABP), using a Pearson correlation between these signals. It is worth noting that in the platform, these signals are obtained non-invasively (nMxa).

This index can replace Mx in cases where cerebral perfusion pressure is not monitored by clinical choice or technical reasons [5]. The values obtained by nMxa are analyzed to determine the intensity and direction of the relationship between mean ABP and CBFv, quantifying the individual's CA. The nMxa value has reference parameters of 1, 0, and -1, representing, respectively, maximum positive correlation (directly proportional variables), no correlation, and maximum negative correlation (inversely proportional variables), respectively. A lower or negative nMxa value suggests a better functioning of the CA mechanism, indicating that, despite changes in ABP, the CBFV remains within a threshold of 0.3 [4-6].

This work aims to clinically validate the nMxa method on the CAAOs platform by analyzing the difference in nMxa results between 22 Control Patients and 23 Acute Ischemic Stroke Patients. This validation could contribute to multicenter studies on neurological diseases, enabling a precise assessment of the CA mechanism and a better understanding of the pathophysiology of these conditions. Additionally, it could help identify patients at high risk of cerebral hemodynamic disorders.

II. Materials and Methods

A. Data Collection

Data from 45 patients were collected for 5 minutes at rest. The collected signals include continuous ABP, collected using a finometer on the middle finger from one of the hands, the brachial ABP signal acquired from a sphygmomanometer

at the other arm, and bilateral CBFv, obtained using Transcranial Doppler Ultrasound on the middle cerebral artery, both at a sampling rate of 100 Hz.

Among these signals, 48% are from control patients. Control individuals were excluded if they had a history of stroke or transient ischemic attack, diabetes mellitus, hypercholesterolemia, carotid artery stenosis, or smoking within the last five years. Among the total individuals, 52% are patients affected by acute ischemic stroke (AIS), with an average time elapsed between the stroke and data collection of $31 (\pm 11)$ hours. The participants' age range was $64 (\pm 10)$ years, and the gender distribution was 47% male. Among the patients affected by stroke, 57% have comorbidities.

B. Pre-processing of signals in the CAAOs Platform

The ABP and CBFv signals were preprocessed using the CAAOs Platform. The ABP signal was calibrated based on the brachial ABP signal with the 5/95 percentile, previously collected. All signals were synchronized as they are obtained from different instruments and then filtered using a third-order bidirectional Butterworth low-pass filter with a cutoff frequency of 20 Hz [3].

Next, the systole and diastole fiducial peaks are detected for the ABP and bilateral CBFv signals, and all original ABP and CBFv values are replaced by the arithmetic mean of their respective time series, obtaining the Beat-to-Beat signal [3]. Finally, the Beat-to-Beat ABP and bilateral CBFv signals are resampled at 5 Hz using cubic spline interpolation. This preprocessing was based on the WhitePapper for TFA calculation, as it is the most commonly used model [7]. Provided by CARNet, it is used as the recommendations for TFA exactification. Currently, there is no such preprocessing recommendations for nMxa calculation.

Fig. 1. Overview of the general methodology of generating the non-invasive mean flow index (nMxa). The raw recording (A) is averaged into blocks (B). The values from the blocks are then split into epochs (C), and a Pearson's correlation coefficient is calculated for every epoch, and the average of the correlation coefficient from the epochs generates one nMxa final.

To calculate nMxa, firstly, the signals must be segmented into equal intervals, lasting between 3 and 10 seconds, in order to calculate the mean value for each interval and replace the original values with the mean value, as shown in Figure 1A. Afterward, the signal is divided into windows with a duration limited by the total size of the signal, ranging from 1 to 6 windows, and then the Pearson correlation is applied to each window, as shown in Figure 1B. Finally, the simple mean of the Pearson correlation results is taken as the outcome. The parameters were chosen based on a systematic review of the Mx method, which also includes nMxa [6], as shown in Figure 1C.

In this study, ABP and CBFv signals were divided into equal segments of 10 seconds. The replacement of all original ABP and CBFv values with the arithmetic mean of their respective time series was performed while preserving the sampling frequency. Then, the entire signal was segmented into time intervals of the same size (windows), being each with 60 seconds of duration. It was followed by calculating the Pearson correlation between the variables (ABP and CBFv), and then a simple mean was taken from the results, generating the final nMxa value.

D. Statistical Analysis

Initially, the participants were grouped into control patients and AIS patients. For each group, we calculated the means, standard errors, 95% confidence intervals, and standard deviations. After verifying the normality of data distribution and homogeneity between groups, a one-way analysis of variance (one-way ANOVA) statistical test was applied. Values of $p \leq 0.05$ were considered as a significant difference between the nMxa results for the groups. Next, we performed an additional analysis focused on the hemispheres of control patients (group 1), the affected hemisphere of AIS patients (group 2), and the unaffected hemisphere of AIS patients (group 3).

As no significant statistical differences were found between the left and right hemispheres of the control group, the mean of both hemispheres of each control patient was calculated, and then the average value was used in the comparison between the control group, the affected hemisphere of AIS patients, and the unaffected hemisphere of AIS patients.

To assess the statistical difference between the nMxa values obtained for each group, we applied the one-way ANOVA test. After applying ANOVA, if a significant difference occurs in the second analysis, we will subsequently use the Games-Howell Post Hoc test in the case of heterogeneous variance or the Tukey Post Hoc test in the case of homogeneous variance, to determine between which groups the difference occurred. The first analysis involves only two groups, so the Post Hoc test is not necessary. The means are presented with their respective \pm standard deviation (SD).

III. Results

In this study, we present the results of the analyses carried out to validate the nMxa method in the CAAOs platform with control patients and AIS patients through statistical analysis. Table 1 shows the clinical characteristics of the individuals used in the research.

Table 1. Clinical characteristics of AIS patients and control group.

Variables	AIS Patients (N=23)	Control (N=22)
Age, years	62 \pm 11	66 \pm 7
Gender Male, %	10 (43%)	11 (50%)
Thrombolised (r-tPA)	9 (39%)	0
Hypertension	5(22%)	0
Hypercholesteromy	1 (4%)	0
Diabetes mellitos	4 (17%)	0
Atrial fibrillation	1 (4%)	0
Onset to assessment (h)	31 \pm 11	-
NIHSS	8 \pm 5	-
mRS	2 \pm 1.4	-

The table presents the clinical characteristics of the individuals used in the study. Patients from different groups were analyzed, and the quantity and percentage of male individuals in each group are depicted. Relevant health factors such as administration of Thrombolised (r-tPA), prevalence of hypertension, diabetes mellitus, and atrial fibrillation among participants were also investigated and are presented in table. The time elapsed from symptom onset to medical assessment (Onset to assessment - in hours), as well as the NIHSS (National Institutes of Health Stroke Scale) and mRS (Modified Rankin Scale) scores for each subject, were also recorded. These data presented in the above table are crucial for understanding the clinical characteristics of the population used in the study.

For the initial analysis, patients were divided between control and AIS groups, and for the second analysis, they were divided based on hemispheres. In both cases, the data used passed the normality test and the homogeneity of variances test. A statistical difference was observed in the first analysis between the control group and the AIS patient group. Table 2 shows the results for the one-way ANOVA test, as well as means, standard deviation, standard error, and confidence intervals for the first analysis.

Table 2. Statistical measures of nMxa for the first analysis.

nMxa	Mean \pm SD	95% Confidence Interval		Standard Error	ANOVA (p-value)
		Lower Limit	Upper Limit		
AIS (N = 46)	0.37 \pm 0.26	0.29	0.45	0.038	0.02
Control (N = 44)	0.22 \pm 0.32	0.13	0.32	0.048	

Note. The CI of the mean assumes that the sample distribution of the mean follows a t-distribution with N-1 degrees of freedom.

It was observed that the mean value of nMxa for the control group was significantly lower compared to the AIS group. The patients in the control group showed a mean value below 0.3, in line with the expected threshold indicative of good CA, while the patients in the AIS group demonstrated a mean value above 0.3, in line with the expected threshold indicative of impaired CA, according to the evidence found in the specialized literature. Although the data passed the tests of normality and homogeneity, validating the application of the one-way ANOVA test, it was noticed that the control

group exhibited a higher standard deviation relative to the mean, while the AIS group showed a lower. This indicates that, even though the normality criteria were met, the data are well distributed around the mean, as represented graphically in the histogram of figure 2. However, it is relevant to highlight that the 95% confidence interval suggests that the data approach the threshold of 0.3 for nMxa, considered as an indication of good autoregulation.

Fig. 2. Histogram showing the incidence of nMxa values for AIS group and control group.

The results of the second analysis revealed a difference in the mean nMxa values between the control group and both the affected and unaffected hemisphere groups in AIS patients. However, no statistical difference was found among the three groups (control group, affected hemisphere of AIS patients, and unaffected hemisphere of AIS patients). Table 3 shows the results for the one-way ANOVA test, along with descriptive statistical measures from the second analysis.

Table 3. Statistical measures of nMxa for the second analysis

nMxa	AIS-Affected (N = 23)	AIS - Unaffected (n = 23)	Control (n = 22)
Mean + SD	0.37 ± 0.24	0.37 ± 0.28	0.22 ± 0.3
Standard Error	0.050	0.059	0.063
95% CI mean lower limit	0.26	0.25	0.093
95% CI mean upper limit	0.47	0.49	0.36
ANOVA (p-value)	0.09		

Note. The CI for the mean assumes that the sample distribution of the mean follows a t-distribution with N-1 degrees of freedom.

However, there was no difference in the mean value between the affected hemisphere group and the unaffected hemisphere group of AIS patients. The data from the control group showed a mean below 0.3, while the data from the hemispheres of AIS patients demonstrated a mean above 0.3, consistent with the previous analysis. To ensure the validity of the results, the data were subjected to tests of normality and homogeneity, confirming the suitability of applying the

one-way ANOVA test. However, it should be noted that the control group exhibited a higher standard deviation relative to the mean, while the AIS group showed a lower standard deviation relative to its respective mean, although still considerably close. This graphical distribution of data around the mean is represented in the histogram presented in Figure 3. Moreover, the analysis of the 95% confidence intervals revealed a larger overlap between the nMxa results in the hemispheres of AIS patients and the mean of the hemispheres in the control group, compared to the first analysis.

Fig. 3. Histogram showing the incidence of nMxa values for groups: AIS - Affected, AIS - Unaffected, Control.

IV. Discussions

In this study, two analyses were conducted: the first aimed to verify the ability of the nMxa index from the CAAOs platform to distinguish control patients from AIS patients, using both hemispheres of each patient in their respective group; the second aimed to assess the possibility of separating patients into groups of affected hemispheres, unaffected hemispheres, and controls.

The most significant result was observed in the first analysis, demonstrating the capability of the nMxa index on the CAAOs platform to distinguish control patients from AIS patients. This finding was crucial as it indicated a difference in nMxa values between the groups. Interestingly, the p-value obtained in the first ANOVA analysis was 0.02, considerably below the statistical threshold of ($p < 0.05$). This statistically significant difference between the mean values of the control and AIS groups reinforces that the implemented method is capable of distinguishing patients with intact autoregulation from those with impaired CA. AIS patients presented higher nMxa values compared to control patients. This finding is essential as it suggests that using the nMxa index on the CAAOs platform can be considered a reliable marker to differentiate AIS patients from control individuals according to the statistical analysis.

The first analysis showed a low standard error of approximately 0.04, indicating similarity between the samples and the population standard. This suggests that the samples are representative and reliable for providing information about the studied population. Furthermore, the mean values of nMxa for the control and AIS groups were consistent with what was expected based on the systematic review conducted by Sorrentino and colleagues [5] and the systematic review from 2021 [6]. This strengthens the validity

of the nMxa method on the CAAOs platform as a reliable indicator for calculating CA.

However, it is important to note that, despite passing the normality test, the samples exhibited a considerably high standard deviation. While this might seem inconsistent at first glance, it can be mitigated by using the 95% confidence interval. Observing the confidence interval for the AIS group, the lower limit remained at 0.29, which corroborates the threshold of 0.3, considered indicative of intact autoregulation. This indicates that most of the data from the AIS group were above this threshold. On the other hand, the upper limit of the confidence interval for the control group was 0.32, indicating that most nMxa values for this group were below this threshold. Thus, despite the standard deviation pointing to a possible lack of normality in the distribution of the samples, passing the normality and homogeneity tests justifies the application of the ANOVA test. This also means that the statistical test applied for the nMxa method on the CAAOs platform is still valid, and the samples are consistent with what is expected for the population.

The second part of the study also presented relevant aspects related to the nMxa parameter and its ability to differentiate between the studied groups. Similarly, to the first analysis, a low standard error of approximately 0.05 was observed, contributing to the reliability of the obtained data.

The mean values of nMxa for the control group and the AIS-Affected and AIS-Unaffected hemisphere groups also remained consistent with what was expected, maintaining the trend identified previously. However, a new observation drew attention: the mean nMxa value for the AIS-Affected hemisphere group and the AIS-Unaffected hemisphere group showed the same value (0.37 considering their respective standard deviations), differing from the mean for the control group, which remained at 0.22 (± 0.3). This finding indicates similarity in the autoregulation characteristics between the affected and unaffected hemispheres of AIS patients for this study. Suggesting that the presence of the condition directly influences CA only when considering both hemispheres together, possibly a more accurate method of analysis.

Although the results passed the normality test again, the standard deviation remained considerably high. However, unlike the first analysis, the 95% confidence interval could not be used as a mediator in this case. The lower limits for the AIS-Affected and AIS-Unaffected hemisphere groups were 0.26 and 0.25, respectively, while the upper limit for the control hemisphere group (mean of the hemispheres) was 0.36. This suggests that the obtained values may not be in line with the threshold of 0.3 used to indicate good autoregulation, considering the considerable overlap of confidence intervals between the groups.

These results raise questions and hypotheses about the complexity of autoregulation, especially when addressing hemispheres individually and attempting to quantify the complex process of autoregulation based on only one hemisphere. The p-value obtained from the ANOVA in the second analysis was 0.09, considerably above the statistical threshold ($p < 0.05$). This result indicates that there was no statistically significant difference between the group means (control, AIS-Affected, and AIS-Unaffected). This may suggest that the methodology used to approach hemispheres may require adjustments to differentiate more effectively between a hemisphere of an AIS patient and the hemisphere of a control patient or even between affected and unaffected hemispheres. The lack of a gold standard for the Mx or nMxa parameters, and the sensitivity of the results of these indices to changes in these parameters (reference for systematic

review 2021), may have been one of the main limitations of this study.

Taken together, the results from the two analyses generated the hypothesis that, although it is possible to differentiate patients with good CA from those with impaired CA, it may not be feasible to analyze only the affected hemisphere to quantify CA, as regulation occurs as a whole, following the physiological circuitry of the brain and the individual's body as a whole, with both the affected and unaffected hemispheres being directly dependent on each other to quantify an individual's CA.

V. Conclusion

The present study successfully demonstrated the capability of the nMxa method on the CAAOs platform to reliably distinguish control patients from AIS patients. The results indicated that the method in the platform is a reliable tool for differentiating AIS patients from control individuals, providing a promising means to assess cerebral autoregulation. However, the analysis also suggested that the complexity of CA may require a more comprehensive approach, considering both hemispheres for a more accurate evaluation. These findings point out to the need for methodological adjustments in the analysis of hemispheres individually, in order to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the CA process in patients with impaired CA.

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